

ULTRASONIC SPOT WELDING BEHAVIOR OF WOVEN-CF/PPS LAMINATES USING CF/PPS ENERGY DIRECTOR

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to development the ultrasonic spot welding process of CFRTP using flat energy director and carbon fiber reinforced energy director. The materials used for spot welding are woven-CF/PPS laminates and energy director consisting of PPS polymer and spread carbon fiber. It is expected to improve the ultrasonic heating efficiency and the joining strength by using continuous carbon fiber reinforced energy director. The ultrasonic oscillator for ultrasonic spot welding has an oscillation frequency of 40 kHz and a maximum output of 600 W. The welding load and displacement of ultrasonic horn during ultrasonic spot welding were precisely controlled using a servo press unit. The effects of ultrasonic power, pressing force, welding time and types of energy director on ultrasonic welding behavior and joining strength were investigated to obtain the proper welding conditions. The temperature of the joining part during ultrasonic welding was measured by a ultrafine thermocouples. From the experimental results, it was revealed that the volume fraction of carbon fiber in the energy director was significantly affects the ultrasonic welding behavior. From the single lap shear strength test results, it was found there was proper fiber volume fraction in energy director to increase the joining strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) composites which can be manufactured by press-forming, hybrid injection molding and auto tape laying are attracting attention recently in aircraft, automotive and industrial applications [1]. However, CFRTP components have rather simple geometry due to the limited deformation allowed for the reinforcing fibers and high viscosity of thermoplastics. Thus, a joining technology is necessary for the manufacturing process of CFRTP composite structures [2]. The demand of on-site joining without large facilities is also expected for a large-scaled CFRTP structures. Figure 1 shows the various welding technology for advanced thermoplastic composites (TPC). Various welding methods have been studied so far for TPC. These welding methods have different heating sources. The resistance welding method is able to weld large scaled structure using a simple equipment and resistance heating element [3-9]. Therefore, it is used in the production of aircraft components such as A340 and A380. The high frequency induction welding method can heat the carbon fiber in CFRTP laminates directly by using induction heating coil. This welding process is often applied to continuous induction welding process [10-12].

The ultrasonic welding has some advantages such as very short welding time, low power consumption and ease of automation. The ultrasonic welding parameters for CFRTP such as vibration time, power and displacement of the sonotrode has been investigated by Villegas in order to optimize the welding conditions [13, 14].

This study aims to development the ultrasonic spot welding process of CFRTP using carbon fiber energy director. It is expected to improve the ultrasonic heating efficiency and the joining strength by using continuous carbon fiber reinforced energy director. The materials used for spot welding are

woven-CF/PPS laminates and energy director consisting of PPS polymer and spread carbon fiber. The effects of ultrasonic power, pressing force, welding time and types of energy director on ultrasonic welding behavior and joining strength were investigated to obtain the proper welding conditions.

Figure 1: Comparison of welding technology for advanced thermoplastic composites.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

The materials used for the experiment is CF/PPS laminate (TenCate, CETEX[®], CF/PPS). This laminate has 5H sateen weave construction with a resin content of $V_f=45\text{vol.}\%$ and a thickness of $t=1.2\text{mm}$. The PPS resin is semi-crystalline polymer. The result of differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) analysis shown that the glass-transition temperature is $T_g=90^\circ\text{C}$, and the melting temperature is $T_m=290^\circ\text{C}$. The result of thermogravimetric analysis (TG) also shown that the decomposition temperature is $T_d=410^\circ\text{C}$.

In this study, three kinds of thin films were used for the energy director as shown in Figure 2. One is a PPS polymer film namely Flat-ED as shown in Figure 2(b). The other is carbon fiber reinforced PPS film namely CF-ED[1] and CF-ED[2] as shown in Figure 2(c) and (d). The any sheet of spread carbon fiber were laminated in the identical fiber direction and used as CF-ED. CF-ED[1] has 0.15 mm thickness and 55 vol% in fiber content, and CF-ED[2] has 0.5 mm thickness and 10 vol% in fiber content.

	Joining target	Energy director		
ID	(a) Woven-CF/PPS	(b) Flat-ED	(c) CF-ED[1]	(d) CF-ED[2]
V_f	45 vol%	0 vol%	55 vol%	10 vol%
t	1.2 mm	0.2 mm	0.15 mm	0.5 mm
Surface image				

Figure 2: Surface images of woven-CF/PPS and various energy directors.

2.2 Manufacturing process of energy director

Figure 3 shows the manufacturing process of various energy director using hot press and punching die. This process is divided into three steps. Firstly, an arbitrary number of PPS films and spread carbon fibre sheets were laminated in metallic mold (Figure 3(i)). Secondly, stacked sheet materials were pressing were pressed by hot pressing machine (Figure 3(ii)). Then, matrix polymer was melted gradually, and spread carbon fibers was impregnated with PPS polymer. Finally, the molding part was punched into a shape of 9.5 mm in diameter using carbide punch and a die (Figure 3(iii)). The reason for punching out the energy director is to stabilize the melting behaviour during the ultrasonic welding.

Figure 3: Manufacturing process of various energy directors.

2.3 Ultrasonic spot welding method

Figure 4 shows the appearance of ultrasonic spot welding device for thermoplastic composites. The test specimens with $W=20$ mm in width and $L=60$ mm in length were prepared. The joining area was insofar as $L_j=20$ mm from the end of laminates, and Flat-ED or CF-ED were used as energy director. The fiber direction of CF-ED[1] and CF-ED[2] was placed in the longitudinal direction of woven-CF/PPS laminates. The test piece was pressurized by the servo press unit (Dai-Ichi Dentsu Ltd., DSP3000) through the ultrasonic horn, and the welding load (P_w) and displacement (δ) were precisely controlled by the servo press. When the ultrasonic power obtained by an ultrasonic generator (Pearl Kogyo Co., Ltd., P600II) was input to Bolt-clamped Langevin Type Transducer (BLT), infinitesimal ultrasonic vibration was generated quickly. Then, the vibration was amplified by original metallic booster and horn. Subsequently, the polymer of energy director and laminates were melted rapidly by frictional heat. After cooling and solidification of the polymer, the joining specimen was obtained. In this study, the effects of welding load (P_w) on ultrasonic welding behaviour, joining part temperature and joining strength were investigated under the various welding conditions as shown in table 1.

Figure 4: Appearance of ultrasonic spot welding device for thermoplastic composites.

Table 1: Ultrasonic spot welding condition of CF/PPS laminate.

Press time, t_p [s]	8.0
Oscillation time, t_o [s]	1.0
Ultrasonic power, P [%]	50
Welding load, P_w [kN]	0.1~1.0

2.4 Evaluation method

In order to evaluate the heating behaviour of welding part, the temperature of welding part was observed by using a thin thermocouples (Ishikawa trading Co., Ltd., K-type, $D=0.076$ mm) and data logger (Graphtech Co., Ltd., GL240) as shown in Figure 4.

The tensile shear strength test was carried out to evaluate a joint strength by using universal testing machine (Shimadzu Co., Ltd., AG250kN XDplus). Then, the cross-head speed was 0.5 mm/min. Figure 5 shows the schematic drawing of single lap joining test specimen. Before tensile shear strength test, Al tabs were bonded to end of specimens with epoxy adhesive. The maximum load obtained during the tensile shear strength test was evaluated. After tensile shear strength test, the fracture face was observed by scanning electron microscope (JEOL Ltd., JSM-6510A), and the welding area of joining part analysed by image analysis.

Figure 5: Schematic drawing of single lap tensile shear test specimen.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Behavior of displacement, welding load and temperature

Figure 6 shows the behaviour of displacement, welding load and temperature of welding part using Flat-ED and CF-ED [1] as energy director. The welding load was also $P_w=0.5$ kN constantly. The position where the horn tip contacts the surface of the woven CF/PPS laminates is $\delta=0$ mm. When the ultrasonic horn tip was contacted the woven-CF/PPS laminates at $t=3.5$ s, the welding area was increased $P_w=0.5$ kN. Then, the welding part was heated significantly, because the ultrasonic vibration was oscillated continuously at $t=4$ s. This is due to the friction heat and the internal heat generation of the polymer caused by the ultrasonic vibration of the energy director. Subsequently, it was found that the welding load was decreased temporarily, and the displacement was increased exponentially because the temperature of welding part was achieved the melting temperature of PPS. From the result of temperature monitoring, the welding part was cooled down naturally after ultrasonic oscillation.

Figure 6: Ultrasonic welding behavior using Flat-ED or CF-ED[1] energy director at $P_w=0.5\text{kN}$.

Figure 7 shows the schematic drawing of ultrasonic spot welding behavior for thermoplastic composites. This ultrasonic welding behavior is divided into the five steps. Firstly, the welding part was pressed with the preset load by using the electric servo press machine. Secondary, the energy director was vibrated ultrasonically by using the ultrasonic generator, BLT and the horn. Then, the polymer in the energy director was heated rapidly. Thirdly, the polymer was heated above melting temperature. Subsequently, the polymer of energy director and laminates were melted. Fourth, the ultrasonic oscillation was turned off, and the polymer was cooled down to below the glass transition temperature. Finally, the welding part was unloaded, then the joining specimen was obtained.

Figure 7: Schematic diagram of ultrasonic spot welding behavior.

3.2 Effects of welding peak temperature

Figure 8 shows the effects of welding load on welding peak temperature at various welding load bonded by using Flat-ED and Flat-ED[1]. The welding peak temperature was increased with increasing the welding load. In the case of using Flat-ED, the temperature was achieved above the melting temperature of PPS polymer. This is because the thermocouple was heated ultrasonically. In the case of using CF-ED[1] at $P_w=0.1\text{ kN}$, it was found that the temperature was above $T=400^\circ\text{C}$ because fixing force of the joining part of woven-CF/PPS laminates was insufficiency. In the case of $P_w>0.2\text{ kN}$, the temperature decreased under 400°C , and the temperature was increased gradually. From these experimental facts, it was considered that the ultrasonic energy was concentrated on the energy director as the welding load increased. It was also seen that the welding peak temperature of Flat-ED specimen was higher than that of CF-ED[1]. Therefore, it was considered that the amount of heat generation depended on the fiber volume fraction in energy directors. It is necessary to optimize the amount of carbon fiber inside the energy director.

Figure 8: Effects of welding load on welding peak temperature bonded by using Flat-ED and CF-ED[1].

3.3 Effects of welding load on displacement

Figure 9 shows the effects of welding load on displacement joined by using various energy director. It was found that the maximum displacement was increased linearly with increased welding load. The reason for this, it was considered that the molten polymer was flowed out with increasing the welding load. Moreover, when the welding load was increased significantly, the maximum displacement was increased more than the thickness of energy directors.

Figure 10 shows the schematic diagram and cross-sectional observation images of the welding part at various welding load bonded by using CF-ED[1]. In the case of $P_w \leq 0.3$ kN, the energy director was melted, and the depression of laminate face was not seen around the pressure portion. In the case of $P_w > 0.3$ kN, the depression was occurred on the woven-CF/PPS laminates as shown in Figure 10(b). From these experimental results, it is necessary that the depressions on the laminates surface is prevented as much as possible because the carbon fibers inside the laminate is fractured. Therefore, it is also necessary that the displacement is controlled by servo press machine in order to obtain the proper welding part.

Figure 9: Effects of welding load on maximum displacement using various energy directors.

Figure 10: Schematic diagram of the welding part at varied welding load bonded by using CF-ED[1].

3.4 Effects of welding load on welding area

Figure 11 shows the effects of welding load on welding area. Generally, the welding area was increased increasing the welding load, and it was decreased at a certain load. It was found that the heat generation by ultrasonic vibration was depends on the welding load. It was revealed that the welding area was larger than the tip area of ultrasonic horn because the molten polymer flowed out to non-pressurized area. In the case of using CF-ED[2], the welding area was increased significantly compared to other energy directors, because a large amount of PPS polymer was contained in the energy director. In the case of using CF-ED[1], the welding area was small because the amount of PPS polymer was small. From these experimental results, it was found that the amount of matrix polymer and thickness of energy director was greatly affect the welding area.

Figure 11: Effects of welding load on welding area bonded by using various energy directors.

Figure 12 shows the scan images of peeled face at $P_w=0.1$ kN, $P_w=0.5$ kN. In the case of $P_w=0.1$ kN, it was observed that the energy director moved in-plane direction. The reason for this, the fixing force of laminates by the ultrasonic horn was insufficiency. At that time, the matrix polymer of the edge of laminate were melted as shown in Figure 12(b). When the welding load was $P_w=0.5$ kN, it was not observed the moving the energy director. In the case of using CF-ED[1] and CF-ED[2], it was found that the profile shape of the welding area was spread in an oval shape. The reason was that the binding of carbon fiber in the 90 degree direction was weak.

Figure 12: Scan images of fracture face of welding parts at $P_w=0.1$ kN and 0.5 kN.

3.5 Results of single lap tensile shear test and microscopic observation

Figure 13 shows the Result of single lap tensile shear test of welding part bonded by using Flat-ED, CF-ED[1] and CF-ED[2], and Figure 14 shows the microscopic observation of fracture face of welding part at $P_w=0.5$ kN after single lap shear test. P - δ curve is shown in Figure 13(a). In this results, the welding load was $P_w=0.5$ kN. In the case of CF-ED[2] specimen, the maximum tensile shear load showed the highest load compared with other test specimen. This is because the joining interface was reinforced by continuous carbon fibers in the CF-ED[2], and the PPS polymer was included sufficiently in the energy director. On the other hand, in the case of CF-ED[1] specimen, the tensile shear load was decreased extremely because the matrix polymer was insufficiently in the energy director as shown in Figure 14(d), (e). In the case of Flat-ED specimen, the displacement (δ_i) showed the highest displacement compared with other specimens because the ductile fracture of PPS polymer was occurred as shown in Figure 14(a), (b). From the result of Figure 13(b), it was found that the maximum tensile shear load showed similar tendency to the behaviour of welding area (Figure 11). From these experimental results, it was found that the amount of matrix polymer and thickness of energy director was greatly affect the maximum tensile shar load and displacement.

(a) P - δ curve ($P_w=0.5$ kN)

(b) Effects of welding load on maximum tensile shear strength.

Figure 13: Result of single lap tensile shear test of welding part bonded by using Flat-ED, CF-ED[1] and CF-ED[2].

Figure 14: Microscopic observation of fracture face of welding part at $P_w=0.5$ kN.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to reveal that the ultrasonic spot welding behaviour of woven-CF/PPS laminates using flat energy director and carbon fiber reinforced energy director. The welding load and displacement of ultrasonic horn was controlled precisely by using electric servo press machine. The effects of the welding load (P_w), displacement of horn (δ) and temperature of welding part (T) on welding behaviour were investigated experimentally. From the result of experiments, the ultrasonic spot welding behavior and proper welding conditions were revealed. It was also revealed that the volume fraction of carbon fiber in the energy director significantly affects the ultrasonic welding behavior. It is also necessary that the displacement of ultrasonic horn is controlled by servo press machine in order to obtain the proper welding part. From the single lap shear strength test results, it was found there was proper fiber volume fraction in energy director to increase the joining strength.

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